

Some Substituted-benzenealkanamines induced Reduction in Spontaneous Locomotor Activity in Mice

P. L. KACHROO* and RAJIVE GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 001
and
O. P. SETHI

Department of Pharmacology, Government Medical College, Jammu

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Some substituted-benzenealkanamine hydrochlorides have been synthesised and tested for spontaneous locomotor activity in mice. Most of the test compounds show hypomotor activity but a few show hypermotor activity.

EIGHTEEN substituted-benzenealkanamine hydrochlorides have been synthesised and tested for modification of spontaneous locomotor activity in albino mice. Thirty minutes after the administration of test compounds, all compounds except 1c, 4d and 4g exhibited reduction ranging 10–88% in the spontaneous locomotor activity recorded for 10 min upto a duration for 5.5 h. The results when compared with diazepam (Calmpose) showed 10% less reduction at equiactive doses. Compounds 1c at 2.5 and 3.5 h, 4d at 1.5, 2.5 and 4.5 h, and 4g at 1.5 h intervals showed enhanced spontaneous locomotor activity followed by reduction of the spontaneous locomotor activity as is evident from Table 1.

Some simple substituted-benzenealkanamines were reported to possess antiamebic activity^{1,2}. More complex and *N*-substituted-benzenealkanamines were also synthesised and found to possess appreciable *in vitro* antiamebic activity against axenically grown *E. histolytica*^{3,4}. The presence of methoxy moiety considered essential for physiological activity was successively replaced by the ethoxy moiety with enhanced activity. The length of the alkyl chain on benzene ring and the one carrying N-atom was found to influence activity and secondary nitrogen compounds were more active than those possessing a primary nitrogen

In the present paper, we report the reduction in spontaneous locomotor activity of four different types of benzenealkanamines to work out their effect on locomotory apparatus of the mice.

2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkyl- α -methylbenzenemethanamine hydrochlorides (1) were synthesised from the corresponding 2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylacetophenones by conversion to oximes followed by reduction with Zn/NH₄OH. 2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzeneethanamine hydrochlorides (2) were prepared from the

corresponding 2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes by conversion into the nitrostyrenes by condensation with nitromethane followed by reduction with LiAlH₄. 2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzenepropanamine hydrochlorides (3) and *N*-substituted-2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzenepropanamine hydrochlorides (4) were prepared from the corresponding 2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzenepropanoic acids by conversion to acid chlorides with SOCl₂ and condensation with NH₃ and primary amines, followed by reduction with LiAlH₄. All amines were isolated as hydrochlorides by passing dry HCl through their ethereal solutions.

Spontaneous locomotor activity: Albino mice of either sex weighing between 12–30 g were used. The animals were divided in groups of four and spontaneous locomotor activity was recorded using 6-beam photoactometer (Techno) for duration of 10 and 30 min after the administration of the amine hydrochlorides⁵. The activity was recorded at hourly intervals upto a period of 5.5 h. The motor activity recorded after the administration of the amine hydrochlorides was compared with the control values taken earlier and the percentage reduction or percentage enhancement was calculated. The compounds were water-soluble and were administered intra-peritoneally at 30 mg/kg. Diazepam (Calmpose)

TABLE 1—PERCENTAGE REDUCTION IN LOCOMOTOR AFTER ADMINISTERING AMINE HYDROCHLORIDES IN MICE (n = 4) ACTIVITY RECORDED FOR 10 MIN

Compd. no	Compd	Control count	Percentage reduction over 5 5 h after i.p. administration of test compounds					
			1st h	2nd h	3rd h	4th h	5th h	6th h
1a	R-n-Pr, R'-Et, R''-Me	263	19.39	67.68	22.50	82.52	62.73	
1b	R-n-Pr, R'-Me, R''-Et	327	21.40	37.30	77.06	60.85	78.05	
1c	R-n-Bu, R'-R''-Et	767	76.27	+20.33*	+31.16*	65.44	82.13	
2a	R-R'-R''-Et	543	84.89	67.21	63.35	49.72	49.53	
2b	R-n-Pr, R'-Et, R''-Me	348	72.98	42.80	78.43	87.64	86.49	71.83
2c	R-n-Bu, R'-Me, R''-Et	256	73.82	57.03	81.25	80.85	88.77	
3a	R-Me, R'-R''-Et	315	46.98	66.66	65.07	88.57	88.88	
3b	R-R'-R''-Et	479	60.33	66.59	71.39	87.89	68.68	75.57
3c	R-n-Pr, R'-Et, R''-Me	524	27.67	34.73	44.08	53.05	78.05	
4a	R-Me, R'-R''-Et, R''-n-Bu	474	56.75	50.42	71.51	80.16	56.75	78.83
4b	R-Me, R'-R''-Et, R''-n-hexyl	507	27.02	45.56	65.08	50.49	80.86	44.18
4c	R-Me, R'-R''-Et, R''-p-methoxyphenyl	550	45.45	69.09	74.18	72.0	54.36	
4d	R-Me, R'-R''-Et, R''-p-bromophenyl	279	+10.75*	+13.26*	32.97	+27.24*	22.58	
4e	R-Et, R'-R''-Me, R''-n-butyl	578	10.20	63.14	58.82	70.24	70.41	
4f	R-Et, R'-R''-Me, R''-hexyl	363	76.30	72.53	67.76	73.27	67.49	
4g	R-Et, R'-R''-Me, R''-p-chlorophenyl	391	+8.43*	31.96	43.98	10.41	45.28	
4h	R-Et, R'-R''-Me, R''-p-bromophenyl	460	20.65	40.21	48.04	48.47	49.34	61.25
4i	R-Me, R'-R''-Et, R''-2-phenylethyl	332	18.97	64.75	50.30	45.78	71.38	
	Diazepam (Calmpose) mg/kg							
	10	599	72.5	94.5	100%	94.8	98.8	98.5
	30	683	91.4	90.0	84.3	98.5	98.5	100
	30	716	83.4	97.0	98.9	99.1	99	99.4
	100	618	78.3	99.3	98.0	98.4	99.3	99.8

* Positive values indicate percentage increase in locomotor activity.

10, 30 and 100 mg/kg i.p. was also used for comparison. Most of the amine hydrochlorides exhibited reduction in the spontaneous locomotor activity ranging 10–88% as compared with diazepam 90–100%. The results are presented in Table 1.

Almost all the test compounds showed variable degree of reduction in the locomotor activity of the mice. Compound nos. 1c, 4d and 4g instead of showing the depressant effect, which was evident from reduction in motoractivity, showed enhanced locomotion which was evident due to significant increase in the count of motoractivity found at 3.5 h after the administration of the drug; the hyperactivity started after 2.5 h. In case of 4d and 4g, the maximum hypermotoractivity was recorded at 4.5 and 1.5 h intervals, respectively. The hyperactivity could be due to a direct stimulation of these compounds on the central nervous system or causing hypersensitization of neuromuscular apparatus or due to enhancing the available concentration of acetylcholine at the neuromuscular junction or escape phenomenon. Compound nos. 1a, 1c, 2a, 2b, 2c, 3a, 3b and 4b exhibited 80% reduction; 2b, 2c and 3a were most potent showing 88.67, 88.88 and 87.89% reduction, respectively. Compound 2a showed 84.89% reduction 0.5 h after administration, and 2c showed prolonged activity. The most potent compound of the series showed 8–10% less reduction in locomotion than that of diazepam.

The compounds thus exhibited two types of activities, *i.e.* hypermotor activity (which was short-lived), and hypomotor activity, which could possibly

be due to different sites of action in the central nervous system or peripherally at the motor pathway which controls locomotion. It could be concluded that the predominant activity of the compounds listed in this series showed reduction in the locomotoractivity. In the rating in terms of potency, the primary amine hydrochlorides were found more active than the secondary amine hydrochlorides which is quite contrary to their antiamebic activity where secondary amine hydrochlorides were observed to be more active than the primary amine hydrochlorides. Reduction in the locomotor activity is one of the basis to study the decrease motor performance of the mice, which could possibly be due to a direct depressant action on the motor centres in the cortex or at any other sites along with motor pathways. The series also possesses antiamebic activity so the reduction in the spontaneous locomotor activity may also be due to their direct relaxant effect on the neuromuscular junction.

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